

DEVELOPMENT OF EXTREME-ENVIRONMENT ELECTRONIC INTERFACES THROUGH A MULTILAYER TAPE CAST APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to develop approaches designed to enhance the high temperature thermoelectric behavior of homogenous and composite *n*-type CaMnO₃ multilayer thick films through Nb doping and interfacial structuring. Microstructural analyses highlight defects, and systematic doping with 1% Nb results in increased lattice parameters and carrier concentration. We demonstrate that the homogeneous and composite multilayer samples possess power factor (S^2/ρ) values near their bulk counterparts, and present multilayer tape casting as a strategy to suppress the phonon transport in bulk scale perovskite-type ceramics.

1 INTRODUCTION

Power generation via thermoelectric (TE) energy conversion is an attractive option for improving the efficiency of various technologies as TE devices contain no moving parts, and are capable of directly converting thermal energy such as waste heat into electrical energy in the presence of a thermal gradient. Traditional TE devices based on metallic systems can provide significant power output but are generally restricted to lower temperatures and are not well suited for extreme environments. TE power generation devices based on ceramic systems are better suited for operation at very high temperatures (>1000 K) in air, as they remain chemically stable, but significant improvements in conversion efficiency are still needed. The TE energy conversion performance is usually characterized by a dimensionless figure-of-merit, $ZT = S^2T/\rho\kappa$, where S , T , ρ and κ denote the Seebeck coefficient, absolute temperature, electrical resistivity, and thermal conductivity, respectively. For practical use in applications, a material must exhibit a $ZT \geq 1$, *i.e.*, possess a large S and low ρ and κ . However, these three parameters are interrelated, therefore, increasing S by decreasing the carrier concentration subsequently increases the ρ , adversely affecting the ZT . By decoupling the scattering mechanisms of charge carriers and lattice vibrations (phonons), it is possible to bypass the tight restrictions placed on TE material optimizations.

Lattice thermal conductivity (κ_{ph}) reduction has been shown to be an effective method for improving the ZT of exemplary bulk materials. The κ in a solid material arises from two distinct mechanisms which include heat transferred through electrical conduction and through wave propagation, or phonon transport [1]. In ceramic-based TE materials, the dominant contribution to the total κ is associated with wave propagation through the lattice by a broad spectrum of different frequency heat-carrying phonons, and has been shown to be independent of the relatively minor electrical thermal conductivity (κ_e). The panoscopic reduction of wave propagation through a material

can be garnered through microstructural engineering at the atomic (<5 nm), nano- (5 – 100 nm) and meso-scale (0.1 – 1 μm), where microstructure control is aimed at disrupting phonon transport by acting as scattering mechanisms at each size scale. Grain size reduction, heterostructures, superlattices and multilayers, alloys, and nanocomposites containing second phase particles, platelets or nanowires, have all been shown to suppress phonon heat conduction at all three size scales [2] [3] [4]. Moreover, researchers have shown that phonon transport at the meso-scale can be dramatically reduced by incorporation of distinct interfaces which serve to scatter phonon propagation in p - and n -type systems [5] [6].

A TE device must contain both p - and n -type materials, and it is desirable that they have compatible mechanical, electrical and thermal properties. However, a significant disparity in the ZT exists between p - and n -type ceramic materials, prompting a drive to close the gap by enhancing n -type ceramic materials. n -type CaMnO_3 and other perovskite-like manganite derivatives have large Seebeck coefficients and low electrical resistivities and can be tuned through doping to enhance material properties [7]. Doping with Nb has been shown to enhance the electrical conductivity and reduce thermal conductivity of CaMnO_3 on the atomic scale, improving its ZT [8]. In addition, the size and concentration of dopant has been shown to induce structural distortions, a concept to be exploited in layered composite materials, which could effectively scatter long wavelength (meso-scale) phonons at three possible types of interfaces, semi-coherent, incoherent and coherent, as depicted in Figure 1. It is postulated that additive material deposition approaches that are capable of producing uniform and discrete interfaces could be used to control meso-scale thermal conductivity through scattering by regulating the quantity and location of differently doped interfaces in ceramic coupons. This approach could have significant implications for incorporating layered composite systems into many potential applications including thermoelectrics, photovoltaics, and related technologies, and serve as a route to scale up *low-dimensional* materials, which are not suitable for large scale applications.

Figure 1: Schematic of phonon scattering between discrete layers by three possible types of boundaries: Semi-coherent, Incoherent, and Coherent.

The objective of this study is to systematically explore the effects of Nb-doping in n - CaMnO_3 -based multilayered thick films which have been fabricated as either sequential (homogeneous) or alternating (heterogeneous) tape cast piles for *bulk* applications. For comparison, the TE properties of bulk $\text{CaMn}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0$ and 0.01) samples prepared via traditional solid-state processing were also measured.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Preparation of $\text{CaMn}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_x\text{O}_3$ powders

Polycrystalline precursor $\text{CaMn}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0$ and 0.01) samples were synthesized by solid-state reaction. Commercially available (Alfa Aesar) CaCO_3 (99.95% purity), MnO_2 (99.9% purity) and Nb_2O_5 (99.9985% purity) powders were combined in stoichiometric ratios, then added to a polytetrafluoroethylene jar with de-ionized water and mixed for 24 hrs by planetary ball milling using zirconium oxide grinding media. Each mixture was dried at 373 K for 24 hrs and subsequently calcined in air at 1423 K for 12 hrs. The calcined powders were manually pulverized using a mortar and pestle and then ball milled in de-ionized water for an additional 24 hrs, at which point the fine grain powders were reclaimed and formulated into tape cast slurries and bulk specimens.

2.2 Preparation of tape cast slurry

Tape cast slurries were fabricated by combining the $\text{CaMn}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_x\text{O}_3$ powders with DisperBYK-001, polypropylene carbonate, propylene carbonate, and acetone. The same tape cast formulation was used for each mixture and the respective proportions are given below in Table 1. The resulting slurries were cast into thick films using a doctor-blade set to 0.4 mm and allowed to dry in air.

Table 1: Tape cast formulations.

<i>Constituents</i>	<i>Wet Weight %</i>	<i>Dry Weight %</i>
$\text{CaMn}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_x\text{O}_3$	32.09	80.90
DisperBYK-001	0.54	1.36
Acetone	60.34	0.00
Polypropylene Carbonate	6.53	16.45
Propylene Carbonate	0.51	1.29

2.3 Preparation of tape cast and bulk samples

Multilayer test samples were fabricated by sectioning the thick films into strips and manually stacking them up to 120 layers high, resulting in either sequential or alternating piles with dimensions $\sim 10 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm} \times 7 \text{ mm}$. The two homogenous samples were prepared by sequentially stacking CaMnO_3 or $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$, and the heterogeneous sample consisted of alternating layers of CaMnO_3 and $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$, as illustrated in Figure 2(a). Henceforth, sequential samples are labelled with a single number, *i.e.*, 0, or 1, corresponding to the nominal Nb concentration, and the alternating sample is labelled with two numbers indicating the nominal Nb concentration in each layer, *i.e.*, 0/1.

A hotplate was initially used to bond the green layers at 323 K. The samples were then isostatically cold-pressed at 207 MPa for 30 mins. Each sample was then subsequently clamped under a spring load and dried in air at 373 K, 423 K and 473 K in 24 hr intervals to prevent delamination due to out-gassing. The dried samples were unclamped and sintered in air by heating to 1473 K for 3 hrs, cooled to 1423 K and heated for 24 hrs, then cooled to room temperature in the furnace. Upon removal from the furnace, the samples were cut and polished as illustrated in Figure 2(b).

Bulk samples of CaMnO_3 and $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ were prepared for comparison by combining the reacted powders with 5 wt% polyvinyl acetate as a binder and uniaxially pressing under 4.5 metric tons using a 2.54 cm diameter die. The compacts were then sintered in air following the same sintering profile for the multilayer samples.

Figure 2: (a) Schematic of tape cast stacking technique for preparation of 0/1 alternating pile. (b) Optical image of the 0/1 sample with one face polished.

2.4 Characterization

The crystal structures of homogeneous CaMnO₃ and CaMn_{0.99}Nb_{0.01}O₃ pellets were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Bruker D8 Discover equipped with a Co K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.79 \text{ \AA}$) at 40 mA and 35 kV. Data were collected at room temperature in the range $2\theta = 25 - 70^\circ$. Microstructural and compositional analyses of the samples were performed using a JEOL scanning electron microscope (SEM) fitted with a NORAN EDAX system. Transport property data were collected on samples oriented with the layers aligned perpendicular to the measurement direction. Four-probe Seebeck coefficient and electrical resistivity measurements were done on parallelepiped bars manually cut and polished to dimensions $\sim 6 \text{ mm} \times 4 \text{ mm} \times 4 \text{ mm}$, in a low pressure He atmosphere using a ZEM-3 Seebeck Coefficient/Electrical Resistivity Measuring System (ULVAC-RIKO, Inc., Japan) from 298 K – 1023 K.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 X-Ray diffraction

XRD data for the homogeneous CaMnO₃ and CaMn_{0.99}Nb_{0.01}O₃ samples sintered at 1473 K are shown in Figure 3, and indicate that each composition is single phase with an orthorhombic perovskite structure (space group $Pnma$). All diffraction peaks can be indexed to PDF# 00-050-1746. In the CaMn_{0.99}Nb_{0.01}O₃ sample, the peaks are shifted to lower 2θ angles (Figure 4 inset), corresponding to an increase in cell volume, which suggests that the synthesis was successful in incorporating Nb⁵⁺ ions into the CaMnO₃ lattice. Crystal structure determinations were done by the Reitveld refinement method using TOPAS to obtain lattice constants. Lattice constants for the 0 and 1 samples are $a = 5.289 \text{ \AA}$, $b\sqrt{2} = 5.283 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.295 \text{ \AA}$ and $V = 209.2 \text{ \AA}^3$, and $a = 5.313 \text{ \AA}$, $b\sqrt{2} = 5.318 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.306 \text{ \AA}$ and $V = 212.1 \text{ \AA}^3$, respectively. The lattice parameters a , b and c , and cell volumes all increase with increasing Nb content, as the radius of the 6-coordinated Nb⁵⁺ ion is larger (0.64 \AA) versus the smaller Mn⁴⁺ ion (0.53 \AA). It is anticipated that this slight difference in lattice parameters between the doped and neat CaMnO₃ will result in minor distortions between the interfaces of a sequentially layered composite. This distortion is expected to result in dimensional strain on the composite due to thermal expansion mismatch. However, if this strain is properly balanced, it could prove beneficial as it presents an irregular pathway serving to reduce phonon propagation across the interface.

Figure 3: XRD patterns for multilayer CaMnO_3 (0) and $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ (1).

4.2 Microstructural analysis

Cross-sectional SEM micrographs obtained from the polished face of the homogeneous (0 and 1) and heterogeneous (0/1) samples are shown in Figure 4, highlighting their density. The porosity of the microstructures appears to result from a combination of several structural defects. It is apparent that there are many small, uniform pores on the order of $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ present, along with a few irregularly-shaped larger voids. The smaller pores are typical of packed powder tape cast processing and are associated with degassing and insufficient sintering. The larger voids are defects associated with the processing of the tapes. It is believed that some of the voids seen in the 0/1 sample occurred as a result of differential shrinkage during sintering and are not due to differences in density or coefficient of thermal expansion differences.

Interfaces between the initial layers can also be observed in each of the micrographs, although they are most evident in the 0 sample. The prominence of the interfaces in these samples is likely due to the cold-pressing and spring loading techniques used prior to sintering. In subsequent experiments, this will be replaced in favor of hot-pressing, which is expected to encourage soldering between the layers during sintering. The insets of Figure 4 further indicate that the interfaces are prone to voids and also initiate the cracking in the direction parallel to the pressing axis. Despite having significant microstructural defects, the relative densities of the multilayered samples are only slightly lower than that for the homogenous bulk samples as listed in Table 2, and appear to have sufficiently consolidated to form a continuous solid network for phonon and carrier transport.

Figure 4: SEM micrographs of polished sample cross-sections.

Table 2: Theoretical, calculated and relative densities of multilayer and bulk $\text{CaMn}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0$ and 0.01) samples.

	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Theoretical Density</i> (g/cm^3)	<i>Calculated Density</i> (g/cm^3)	<i>Relative Density</i> (%)
<i>Multilayer</i>	0	4.54	3.316	73.0
	1	4.47	3.257	72.9
	0/1	<i>n/a</i>	3.299	<i>n/a</i>
<i>Bulk</i>	0	4.54	3.613	79.6
	1	4.47	3.437	76.9

4.3 Electrical properties

Figure 5 shows the temperature-dependence of the electrical resistivity (ρ) from 300 – 1000 K for the multilayer and bulk CaMnO_3 and $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ samples. Both undoped samples exhibit semiconductor-like ρ behaviour, which decreases with increasing temperature. It was initially assumed that the multilayered materials would display higher ρ due to the porosity and layer interfaces, however, no correlation between the calculated sample density and electrical resistivity was observed. In fact, the measured ρ of the undoped multilayer sample is about half that of the bulk specimen at 950 K (16 m Ω -cm and 28 m Ω -cm, respectively). The electrical resistivity of the 0/1 and 1 multilayer samples is similar and slightly higher than the bulk 1 sample; all showing reduced temperature dependence and a weak metallic behaviour with Nb substitution. The systematic reduction in the electrical resistivity observed due to Nb doping is expected due to the increase in carrier concentration, however, above 400 K, the ρ of the 0/1 and 1 multilayer samples, which have fewer microstructural defects than the undoped sample by comparison, is larger and will require further examination. Studies have shown that the electron hopping mechanism between Mn^{4+} and Mn^{3+} is responsible for the electrical conductivity behavior observed in doped CaMnO_3 . The occurrence of the Mn^{3+} species is due to a reduction of Mn^{4+} as a result of Nb^{5+} addition as the material attempts to remain isoelectric. As such, the conductivity enhancement with Nb doping has been observed to be proportional to the dopant concentration at lower doping levels (< 3 at.%). This doping also produces changes in the perovskite structure due to increases in the Mn ionic radius, Nb-Mn radius mismatch, and Jahn-Teller distortions.

Figure 5: Electrical resistivity as a function of temperature for the (a) multilayer and (b) bulk CaMnO_3 and $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ samples.

The temperature-dependent Seebeck coefficient (S) was measured simultaneously with the ρ from 300 – 1000 K, and is plotted in Figure 6. S values for each sample indicate n -type conduction with electrons as the dominating carriers over the entire temperature range. In the multilayer samples, at low temperatures, the undoped sample, having the lowest carrier concentration, has the largest $|S|$ value, which incidentally decreases with increasing temperature. For the 1 sample, the S value is reduced but the values increase slightly with increasing temperature. This behavior is not unexpected as the thermopower is generally inversely proportional to the carrier concentration, which further indicates an increase in charge carrier concentration as a result of the change in charge valence described by the Verwey controlled ionic valence principle [9]. When undoped CaMnO_3 is alternately stacked with $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ in the 0/1 sample, the reduction in $|S|$ is still seen, though less pronounced. It is interesting to note that similar to the electrical resistivity behavior, the temperature-dependence of S diminishes. Nb doping has a similar effect in the bulk samples where there is a considerable decrease in $|S|$, and qualitatively agrees with the decrease in ρ . In addition, the moderately large bulk S value of $-149 \mu\text{V/K}$ at 950 K for the 1 sample is virtually identical to the multilayer counterpart.

Figure 6: Comparison of the temperature dependence of S for the (a) multilayer and (b) bulk CaMnO_3 and $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ samples.

Power factor ($PF = S^2/\rho$) calculations are plotted in Figure 7. In the multilayered samples, the PF for the composite 0/1 sample falls about midway between the larger 0 and smaller 1 samples. The large PF of the 0 sample, which reaches a maximum of $240 \mu\text{W/mK}^2$, is primarily due to its lower electrical resistivity. Similarly, the PF for the 0 bulk sample, reaching $200 \mu\text{W/mK}^2$, is larger than the 1 bulk sample, but as a result of the much larger S over the entire temperature range. The difference in PF between the undoped and doped samples is fairly constant at all temperatures. Our values are comparable to and occasionally higher than those found in other rare earth and transition metal doped $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{RE}_x\text{Mn}_{1-y}\text{M}_y\text{O}_3$ systems [10]. The differences are likely due to the variances in the microstructures resulting from sample processing. We acknowledge that the dopant levels in this study were quite low, and can infer from related studies that higher PF s with increased doping are possible.

Figure 7: Temperature dependence of the power factor for the (a) multilayer and (b) bulk CaMnO_3 and $\text{CaMn}_{0.99}\text{Nb}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ samples.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Homogeneous and heterogeneous tape casts of orthorhombic $\text{CaMn}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_x\text{O}_3$ ($x = 0$ and 0.01) were synthesized to form multilayer piles and compared to bulk samples processed by conventional solid-state synthesis. XRD verified that doping with 1% Nb increases the unit cell volume in the multilayer samples, weakly distorting the orthorhombic structure and slightly increasing the Mn^{3+} ion concentration. This increase in carrier concentration affected the electrical properties and had the overall impact of reducing the power factor from the undoped sample. Considering the microstructural defects discussed earlier, it is thought that improvements to the microstructure – through hot-pressing and oxygenation – will allow for clearer trends to emerge. Furthermore, removing one of the thick tape cast layers and implementing an additive material deposition approach such as aerosol atomization should not only produce interlayers closer to an effective thickness for meso-scale phonon scattering, but also dramatically reduce the sample preparation time and quantity of material needed.

We find that our multilayer tape cast homogeneous and heterogeneous samples possess PF values nearly identical to bulk materials that have been prepared by conventional solid-state and sol-gel processing methods. Based on the results of this work, we expect that by further optimization of multilayer composite samples with layers containing varying compositions and/or varying thicknesses will induce small perturbations in the lattice between layers that may result in a uniform scattering region wherein phonon transport is disproportionately decreased relative to electron mobility. With the PF serving as a preliminary figure-of-merit, one can deduce that the multilayer tape cast approach will be an effective route to fostering ZT improvements at high temperatures in calcium manganites and related materials.

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